

VIEWERS PERCEPTION ON TAMIL SERIALS AND DUBBING SERIALS – A STUDY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO UDUMALPET TALUK

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Abstract:

Television is one revolutionary instrument, which has changed the mindset of Indian public in a short span of time. From a state controlled, electronic media, today we have free airing multiple channels. The main objective of the study is to study the viewer's perception towards Tamil serials and dubbing serials. The data required for the study have been collected through structured questionnaire in order to assess the level of perception on dubbing serials and tamil serials. A sample of 500 viewers has been chosen for purpose of the study. Convenient sampling method is adopted to select the sample. The statistical technique like Percentage Analysis and Chi-Square was applied for the purpose of data analysis. This study concluded that Women particularly are more interested in the indian culture and lifestyle. The reason being western trends and fashion attract them. They are style conscious, love to flaunt the latest and love to experiment with clothes and latest trends.

Key Words: Television, Perception, Tamil Serials & Dubbing Serials

Introduction:

Television is one revolutionary instrument, which has changed the mindset of Indian public in a short span of time. From a state controlled, electronic media, today we have free airing multiple channels. Due to the strife competition among various T.V. channels, today, India is watching numerous serials on the screen. Apart from infusing consumer culture through its advertisements and trickling buyer mentality, T.V. has also produced many anti-social elements. In short, it is both positive and negative.

Movies and TV serials are replete with brands these days. It is a multimillion dollar business with every frame in a movie or TV serial having an opportunity for branding. Movies and TV serials include placements of all kinds of products, be it cars, cell phones, mouth fresheners, branded tea or almost any other category. A few instances from international as well as Indian movies and TV serials are presented to exemplify the prevalence of product placements.

The broadcast of the teleserials on the Government owned television network was not the incident in isolation before the country. There were several pressing issues before the nation during the period of the broadcast. The historical matrix can provide a context to make sense of the making of a phenomenon of the serials. We can identify at least three significant parallel developments in the nation, more or less, continuing with serials on doordarshan and they seem to project a relationship of causality.

Review of Literature:

Borae Jin and Joohan Kim (2015) , “Television Drama Viewing and Romantic Beliefs: Considering Parasocial Interaction and Attachment Style”. This study examined the relationships between attachment styles, drama viewing, parasocial interaction, and romantic beliefs. A survey of students revealed that drama viewing was weakly but negatively related to romantic beliefs, controlling for parasocial interaction and attachment styles. Instead, parasocial interaction mediated the effect of drama viewing on romantic beliefs.

Dr. Sapna Premchandani (2015), “A Discriminant Analysis of Viewers' Perception towards Prime Time Television Shows with special reference to Indore”. The main objectives of the study is to study viewer's perception towards prime time television views. The study was descriptive in nature. Statistical tool like KMO and discriminant analysis was applied. The study was carried on 174 prime time TV viewers in Indore, who were selected on random basis.

Abdul Rauf Ridzuan and Rosilawati Sultan Mohideen (2016), “A Study of Usage Patterns and TV Shows Analysis on Internet Tv”. The purpose of this study is to explore how the Internet TV has become significant among young people in Malaysia. Therefore, the objective of this study is to identify the new usage patterns of Internet TV which include time spend, preferred TV shows and feedback about the famous phrase “anytime and anywhere”. A quantitative analysis was used in this study. The study found that young people's usage pattern and practices on Internet TV are slightly different compared to conventional TV.

Orgin of the Research Problem:

Media and society both are inter-related and affect each other in many ways. Sometimes media communication is guided by society and sometimes media have dominance over society. The media affects the mind of people in such a manner that their thinking, perception and ideas are changed. Television was seen as a catalyst of social change and national development, sensitizing society about social justice, educating the population and developing and uplifting its human resources.

The T.V. serial does have an impact on the T.V. viewers which has been inbuilt in their making. In view of the fact that Television in India is fast developing as a major source of Mass enlightenment, leisure and pleasure, it is essential that its impact in various areas is analyzed. In terms of critics, comments and reviews no other medium, print, radio, cinema, caught the fancy of the analysts television. This may only be evident if we study the impact of T.V. serials on social attitudes and examine these with viewing preference of TV Viewers in Udumalpet Taluk.

Scope of the Study:

Television serials have increasingly become popular in Tamilnadu. In the last decade, the adaption and production of serialized television fiction has become a major feature in television programming. The research therefore looked at the genre of television serials and provided information on the role these serials play in the character formation of peoples and in shaping their conception of reality. The findings of this research could be useful in understanding differences in response across various subgroups of viewers, as also between the TV serials. This study is used to analyse the viewer's perception on tamil and dubbing serials in Udumalpet Taluk. This study is especially designed to know that factors influencing the perception on Tamil and Dupping serials their level of satisfaction.

Objectives of the Study:

The following are the objectives of the study

- ✓ To study the viewer's perception towards Tamil serials and dubbing serials.
- ✓ To find out the preference of viewing based on channels and programmes viewed with respect to demographic profiles.

Research Methodology:

Methodology the external environment constitutes the research by giving an in depth idea on setting the right research objective, followed by literature point of view, based on that chosen analysis through interviews or questionnaires findings will be obtained and finally concluded message by this research.

On the other hand from the methodology, the internal environment constitutes by understanding and identifying the right type of research, sampling method, sampling size, method of data collection followed by right procedures and techniques based on his or her research work.

Hypothesis of the Study:

In tune with the objective of the study, the following null hypotheses have been framed to test their association with the following variables. The null hypotheses are:

Level of Perception on Tamil Serials:

- ✓ There is no significant association between gender of the respondents and their level of perception on tamil serials.
- ✓ There is no significant association between age of the respondents and their level of perception towards Tamil serials.
- ✓ There is no significant association between area of residence of the respondents and their level of perception on tamil serials.
- ✓ There is no significant association between marital status of the respondents and their level of perception on Tamil serials.
- ✓ There is no significant association between Educational Qualification of the respondents and their level of perception on Tamil serials.
- ✓ There is no significant association between occupation of the respondents and their level of perception on Tamil serials.
- ✓ There is no significant association between type of family of the respondents and their level of perception on Tamil serials.
- ✓ There is no significant association between number of members in the family and their level of perception on Tamil serials.
- ✓ There is no significant association between annual income of the respondents and their level of perception on Tamil serials.

Level of Perception on Dubbing Serials:

- ✓ There is no significant association between gender of the respondents and their level of perception on dubbing serials.
- ✓ There is a significant association between age of the respondents and their level of perception towards dubbing serials.

- ✓ There is no significant association between area of residence of the respondents and their level of perception on dubbing serials.
- ✓ There is no significant association between marital status of the respondents and their level of perception on dubbing serials.
- ✓ There is no significant association between Educational Qualification of the respondents and their level of perception on dubbing serials.
- ✓ There is no significant association between occupation of the respondents and their level of perception on dubbing serials.
- ✓ There is no significant association between type of family of the respondents and their level of perception on dubbing serials.
- ✓ There is a significant association between number of members in the family and their level of perception on dubbing serials.
- ✓ There is a significant association between annual income of the respondents and their level of perception on dubbing serials.

Sampling Method:

The sampling used for the study is convenient sampling. This sampling is selected by the researcher for the purpose of convenience to access. A pilot study is conducted to validate the questionnaire and to confirm the feasibility of the study. Based on the pilot study, the questionnaire is modified suitably to elicit response from the sample group.

Sampling Size:

The data required for the study have been collected through structured questionnaire in order to assess the level of perception on Tamil serials and dubbing serials. A sample of 500 viewers has been chosen for purpose of the study.

Method of Data Collection:

The data for this study are of two types: -

- ✓ Primary data
- ✓ Secondary data

Primary Data:

Primary data is the data is collected from the respondent for the first time, it is original in nature. For the purpose of collection of primary data, a well structured questionnaire was framed and filled by the respondents. The questionnaire comprises of close ended as well as open ended questions.

Secondary Data:

Secondary data are collected from books, magazines, web sites etc, and both open ended & close-ended questions are incorporated in the questionnaire for the collection of data.

Framework of Analysis:

The following analysis tools used in the study

- ✓ Percentage Analysis
- ✓ Chi – square test

Percentage Analysis:

Percentage refers to a special kind of ratio in making comparison between two or more data and to describe relationships. There are 24 independent variables are taken here the analysis for summarised table following given below in table 1.

$$\text{Percentage of Respondents} = \frac{\text{Number of Respondents}}{\text{Total Respondents}} \times 100$$

Table 1: Social Economic Profile

S.No	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percent
1	Age		
	Below 20 Years	76	15.2
	20 – 35 Years	206	41.2
	35 – 50 Years	150	30.0
	50 Years above	68	13.6
	Total	500	100
2	Area of Residence		
	Urban	167	33.4
	Semi – Urban	205	41.0
	Rural	128	25.6
	Total	500	100
3	Gender		
	Male	209	41.8

	Female Total	291 500	58.2 100
4	Marital Status Married Unmarried Total	338 162 500	67.6 32.4 100
5	Educational Qualification Upto HSC Under Graduate Post Graduate Professional Others Total	130 187 63 70 50 500	26.0 37.4 12.6 14.0 10.0 100
6	Occupation Agriculture Business Government sector employees Private sector employees Professional Home maker Total	89 81 79 94 52 105 500	17.8 16.2 15.8 18.8 10.4 21.0 100
7	Nature of the family Joint Nuclear Total	236 264 500	47.2 52.8 100
8	Members of family 1 – 3 Members 3 – 5 Members Above 5 Members Total	86 279 135 500	17.2 55.8 27.0 100
9	Annual Income Below Rs.50,000 Rs.50,000 – 1,00,000 Rs.1,00,000 – 3,00,000 Rs.3,00,001 – 5,00,000 Total	59 212 153 76 500	11.8 42.4 30.6 15.2 100
10	Profession Doctor/Engineer Housewife Govt.job / Retired Student Farmer/Artisan/laborers Total	79 143 112 84 82 500	15.8 28.6 22.4 16.8 16.4 100
11	Frequency of viewing TV in a week 7 days a week 6 days a week 5 days a week 4 days a week 3 days a week 2 days a week Once a week Rarely Total	76 59 85 119 82 48 18 13 500	15.2 11.8 17.0 23.8 16.4 9.6 3.6 2.6 100
12	Timing of watching television In the morning In the noon In the evening In the night Total	66 98 206 130 500	13.2 19.6 41.2 26.0 100

13	Time spent on watching television		
	Less than 30 minutes	45	9.0
	Between 30 minutes -1 hour	166	33.2
	Between 1 – 2 hours	253	46.6
	More than 2 hours	56	11.2
	Total	500	100
14	Place of watching television		
	At home	319	63.8
	At neighbours house/work place	181	36.2
	Total	500	100
15	Most watching TV Programmes		
	News based programmers	32	6.4
	News	57	11.4
	Sports	63	12.6
	Serials	140	28.0
	Film based programmers	51	10.2
	Films	84	16.8
	Film songs/albums	62	12.4
	Documentaries	7	1.4
	Others	4	.8
	Total	500	100
16	Most watching Tamil TV channels		
	Sun TV	155	31.0
	Z Tamil	102	20.4
	Polimer TV	141	28.2
	Jaya TV	25	5.0
	Vijay TV	77	15.4
	Total	500	100
17	Most preferred programs of the respondents		
	Vani Rani	110	22.0
	Puthuputhu Arthangal	164	32.8
	Saravanan Meenakshi	142	28.4
	Uravey Uyire	84	16.8
	Total	500	100
18	Most preferred TV serials		
	Mundru muduchu	43	8.6
	Sithaiyinraman	104	20.8
	Erumalargal	79	15.8
	Theivam thantha veedu	129	25.8
	Kalyanam mudhal kadhala varai	83	16.6
	Others	62	12.4
	Total	500	100
19	Frequently of watching Tamil serials		
	5 days a week	116	23.2
	4 – 3 days a week	164	32.8
	2 – 1 days a week	98	19.6
	Occasionally	122	24.4
	Total	500	100
20	Watching Number of Episodes of tamil serials		
	All the episodes	159	31.8
	Only few of the episodes	215	43.0
	Most of the episodes	126	25.2
	Total	500	100
21	Patterns of watching dubbing serials		
	With family members	342	68.4
	Alone with friends	158	31.6
	Total	500	100

22	Nature of watching tamil serial	292	58.4
	I Watch tamil serials without any distraction	208	41.6
	While watching tamil serials I for quite a few other things	500	100
	Total		

Chi – Square Test:

The chi square test is an important test among the several tests of signification developed by satisfaction. Chi-square, symbolically written χ^2 is a statistical measure used in the contexts of sampling analysis for comparing a variance to a theoretical variance. It can also be used to make comparison between theoretical population and actual data when categories as used. In this study perception of viewers is analysed. For that purpose the variables Gender, Age, Area of residence, marital status, Educational qualification, Occupation, Type of family, Members of family, Annual Income are taken and compared with perception level. The details are summarised following table 2 and table 3. The formula applied for Chi-square

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

O_i = Observed Frequency

E_i = Expected frequency

Table 2: Demographic Profile and level of perception in Tamil serials

S.No	Variables	Good	Satisfactory	Poor	Total	D.f	Calculated χ^2 Value	Table Value	Result
1	Age					6	2.560	12.592	Not Significant
	Below 20 years	28	27	21	76				
	20 – 35 years	86	55	65	206				
	35 – 50 years	61	47	42	150				
	Above 50 years	26	21	21	68				
	Total	201	150	149	500				
2	Area of Residence					4	1.538	9.488	Not Significant
	Urban	70	48	49	167				
	Semi – Urban	76	66	63	205				
	Rural	55	36	37	128				
	Total	201	150	149	500				
3	Gender					2	0.569	5.991	Not Significant
	Male	88	60	61	209				
	Female	113	90	88	291				
	Total	201	150	149	500				
4	Marital Status					2	1.001	5.991	Not Significant
	Married	132	106	100	338				
	Unmarried	69	44	49	162				
	Total	201	150	149	500				
5	Educational qualification					8	7.886	15.507	Not Significant
	Upto HSC	53	39	38	130				
	Under Graduate	67	60	60	187				
	Post Graduate	33	14	16	63				
	Professional	32	20	18	70				
	Others	16	17	17	50				
	Total	201	150	149	500				
6	Occupation					10	11.979	18.307	Not Significant
	Agriculture	41	22	26	89				
	Business	38	26	17	81				
	Government sector employees	33	23	23	79				
	Private sector employees	34	28	32	94				
	Professional	13	17	22	52				
	Home maker	42	34	29	105				
	Total	201	150	149	500				
7	Nature of the family					2	0.796	5.991	Not Significant
	Joint Family	90	73	73	236				
	Nuclear Family	111	77	76	264				
	Total	201	150	149	500				
8	Members of family					4	2.408	9.488	Not Significant
	1 – 3 Members	38	24	24	86				
	3 – 5 Members	110	80	89	279				
	Above 5 Members	53	46	36	135				
	Total	201	150	149	500				
9	Annual Income					6	15.520	12.592	Significant
	Below Rs.50,000	24	16	19	59				
	Rs.50,000 – 1,00,000	84	57	71	212				
	Rs.1,00,000 – 3,00,000	61	49	43	153				
	Rs.3,00,001 – 5,00,000	32	28	16	76				
	Total	201	150	149	500				

However, as the calculated χ^2 value is greater than the table at five percent level, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it is concluded that there is a significant association between annual income of the respondents and their level of perception on Tamil serials.

Table 3: Demographic Profile and level of perception in dubbing serials

S.No	Variables	Good	Satisfactory	Poor	Total	D.f	Calculated χ^2 Value	Table Value	Result
1	Age								
	Below 20 years	27	21	28	76	6	13.052	12.592	Significant
	20 – 35 years	85	65	56	206				
	35 – 50 years	64	42	44	150				
	Above 50 years	26	21	21	68				
Total	202	149	149	500					
2	Area of Residence								
	Urban	69	49	49	167	4	0.524	9.488	Not Significant
	Semi – Urban	79	63	63	205				
	Rural	54	37	37	128				
	Total	202	149	149	500				
3	Gender								
	Male	86	61	62	209	2	0.097	5.991	Not Significant
	Female	116	88	87	291				
Total	202	149	149	500					
4	Marital Status								
	Married	140	100	98	338	2	0.512	5.991	Not Significant
	Unmarried	62	49	51	162				
Total	202	149	149	500					
5	Educational qualification								
	Upto HSC	46	38	46	130	8	7.080	15.507	Not Significant
	Under Graduate	72	60	55	187				
	Post Graduate	31	16	16	63				
	Professional	34	18	18	70				
	Others	19	17	14	50				
Total	202	149	149	500					
6	Occupation								
	Agriculture	39	26	24	89	10	19.929	18.307	Significant
	Business	36	17	28	81				
	Government sector employees	30	23	26	79				
	Private sector employees	34	32	28	94				
	Professional	20	22	10	52				
	Home maker	43	29	33	105				
	Total	202	149	149	500				
7	Nature of the family								
	Joint Family	94	73	69	236	2	0.276	5.991	Not Significant
	Nuclear Family	108	76	80	264				
	Total	202	149	149	500				
8	Members of family								
	1 – 3 Members	32	24	30	86	4	16.761	9.488	Significant
	3 – 5 Members	120	89	70	279				
	Above 5 Members	50	36	49	135				
Total	202	149	149	500					
9	Annual Income								
	Below Rs.50,000	21	19	19	59	6	16.079	12.592	Significant
	Rs.50,000 – 1,00,000	86	71	55	212				
	Rs.1,00,000– 3,00,000	63	43	47	153				
	Rs.3,00,001 – 5,00,000	32	16	28	76				
Total	202	149	149	500					

However, as the calculated χ^2 value is greater than the table at five percent level, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it is concluded that there is a significant association between age, occupation, Members of family and annual income of the respondents and their level of perception on dubbing serials.

Findings:

Chi – Square Test:

Variables Associated With Level of Perception on Tamil Serials:

- ✓ Therefore, it is concluded that there is no significant association between age of the respondents and their level of perception towards Tamil serials.
- ✓ Therefore it is concluded that there is no significant association between area of residence of the respondents and their level of perception on tamil serials.
- ✓ Therefore it is concluded that there is no significant association between gender of the respondents and their level of perception on tamil serials.
- ✓ Therefore it is concluded that there is no significant association between marital status of the respondents and their level of perception on Tamil serials.

- ✓ Therefore it is concluded that there is no significant association between Educational Qualification of the respondents and their level of perception on Tamil serials.
- ✓ Therefore, it is concluded that there is no significant association between occupation of the respondents and their level of perception on Tamil serials.
- ✓ Therefore it is concluded that there is no significant association between type of family of the respondents and their level of perception on Tamil serials.
- ✓ Therefore, it is concluded that there is no significant association between number of members in the family and their level of perception on Tamil serials.
- ✓ Therefore, it is concluded that there is a significant association between annual income of the respondents and their level of perception on Tamil serials.

Variables Associated With Level of Perception on Dubbing Serials:

- ✓ Therefore, it is concluded that there is a significant association between age of the respondents and their level of perception towards dubbing serials.
- ✓ Therefore it is concluded that there is no significant association between area of residence of the respondents and their level of perception on dubbing serials.
- ✓ Therefore it is concluded that there is no significant association between gender of the respondents and their level of perception on dubbing serials.
- ✓ Therefore it is concluded that there is no significant association between marital status of the respondents and their level of perception on dubbing serials.
- ✓ Therefore it is concluded that there is no significant association between Educational Qualification of the respondents and their level of perception on dubbing serials.
- ✓ Therefore, it is concluded that there is a significant association between occupation of the respondents and their level of perception on dubbing serials.
- ✓ Therefore it is concluded that there is no significant association between type of family of the respondents and their level of perception on dubbing serials.
- ✓ Therefore, it is concluded that there is a significant association between number of members in the family and their level of perception on dubbing serials.
- ✓ Therefore, it is concluded that there is a significant association between annual income of the respondents and their level of perception on dubbing serials.

Suggestions:

- ✓ Religion is displayed in a negative light, and separation of religion from life is advocated
- ✓ Adversely affecting the morals of young people and their attitudes, especially in adolescence
- ✓ Presentation of extreme cultural differences
- ✓ Suggesting the idea that life is easy and free of responsibilities
- ✓ Spreading inaccurate ideas about the traditions and values of Islamic communities
- ✓ Encouraging distraction and laziness. For example, "it does not help the younger generation to develop and innovate".
- ✓ Serials counterfeit reason the cultural and intellectual invasion, such as dubbed serials affect the behavior of young people.

Conclusion:

Tamil content is most popular among the four South Indian languages and sees a lot of traction with the international audiences. Tamil Nadu having a youth population of more than 1.26 crore has a huge potential for launching a Youth General Entertainment Channel. There lies a gap between the male youth and the existing TV channels. So a strong need exists for launching a new channel exclusively for male youth. From the survey results, we can conclude that the preference for male youth include programs based on music, comedy, movies and knowledge based programs. But with respect to women it includes serials, music, daily shows, dance/singing shows and also dubbed content (Tamil/dubbing). There is natural curiosity of audiences to understand North Indian cultures, traditions & weddings. Adaptation and dubbing of successful fiction and non-fiction shows from Tamil General Entertainment Channel to regional languages continue to have reasonable success both in terms of viewership and cost optimization.

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